

Deliverable

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1 Introduction

The primary goal of PRO-Ethics was to create a comprehensive, collaboratively developed *ethics framework and guidelines* to support the implementation of participatory activities and management of ethical aspects in research and innovation processes. Most prominently, this document focuses on the involvement of non-traditional stakeholders in the activities of research and innovation funding agencies (RFOs). Through this, PRO-Ethics aimed to enhance the relevance, equity, and efficiency of research and innovation endeavours. The activities organised during the project's runtime were specifically designed to achieve this goal, encompassing all necessary steps – including peer learning, testing, validation, etc. – to guarantee the utmost quality of the *ethics framework and guidelines* and a wide uptake across the targeted stakeholder communities. In this sense, one of the core activities to broadly disseminate the project results was the final conference, as an international event to bring together all stakeholders involved in creating the *ethics framework* and representatives of all user groups with a stake in implementing it in their research and innovation activities.

The 'Connect. Collaborate. Create.' Conference, an event jointly organized by the PRO-Ethics and COESO projects on 19-21 October 2023 in Paris at Aubervilliers Campus Condorcet, sought to set forward new initiatives involving participatory research and citizen science in Europe. Envisioned as more than just a presentation of project results, it was designed to pioneer new frontiers in ethical citizen engagement, participatory research, and the broadening of dialogues across international networks. It aimed to bridge communities, fostering an environment where ethical collaboration and co-creation are not just concepts but active practices that drive innovation and engagement in research.

Recognizing the pivotal role that ethical considerations play in participatory research, the conference sought to elevate these discussions to the European stage, inviting a diverse array of voices to contribute to a narrative. The unique blend of stakeholders – ranging beyond researchers, from research funding organisations (RFOs) and policymakers to industry representatives, civil society organizations (CSOs), and citizens – reflected the conference's commitment to inclusivity and diversity. In total, 218 people registered to the conference, with approximately 170 managing to attend on site.

Drawing inspiration from the 'un-conference' approach, the event was designed to be organised by and for its attendees, offering a platform where every participant could contribute to shaping the agenda. This approach, reminiscent of the THATCamp¹ (The Humanities and Technology Camp) model, encouraged spontaneous collaboration and dialogue, breaking away from the traditional confines of structured academic conferences. The conference's innovative format was instrumental in fostering a sense of ownership and active participation among attendees, and thus guaranteeing good turnout. This format also aligns with principles of ethical participatory research and citizen science, which advocate for decentralising knowledge creation and promoting wider engagement in research processes.

The 'Connect. Collaborate. Create.' Conference was a journey towards a more engaged, ethical, and inclusive future in research and innovation. This report seeks to provide more insights into its vision, the intensive work carried out for bringing it to life by a team composed of representatives from both projects, and the instruments for communicating and disseminating the event before, during and after its implementation. The final section discusses experiences from the participants and a summary of the main results.

¹ While no longer active, information on THATCamp can be found here: <https://thatcamp.org/>

2 Conference aims and objectives

At the design phase of the project, the PRO-Ethics consortium aimed to organise a final conference that goes beyond increasing the uptake of the project results and raises awareness on the importance of an ethical baseline for citizens' involvement, while stimulating international network-building and critical dialogue, fostering the integration of results into practice and broadening commitment to ethical stakeholder engagement. The consortium also set out to involve a broad variety of relevant stakeholders across Europe and beyond, including researchers, funding agencies, EU- and national policymakers, industry representatives, citizens and CSOs, and ethics and integrity bodies.

To respond to these objectives, the 'Connect. Collaborate. Create' Conference – organised as a partnership between PRO-Ethics and the COESO projects, and developed to address the objectives of both projects – aimed to serve as a bridge for communities to:

- ▶ foster ethical participatory approaches to research and research funding
- ▶ activate participatory research and citizen science involving the social sciences and humanities

Serving to the fulfilment of these goals, the conference sought to promote conversations and insights on six core areas:

- ▶ Participatory research, citizen science, and open science networks and infrastructures
- ▶ Support services for participatory research and citizen science
- ▶ Methodologies for doing and teaching citizen science and ethical participatory approaches to research, including in funding agencies
- ▶ Data workflows and communication formats
- ▶ Drivers and barriers for implementing, supporting, and funding citizen science, as well as participation in the processes of funding agencies
- ▶ Assessing and evaluating participatory processes

2.1 Creating a conference by and for its attendees

In response to these aims, the conference organising team aimed to apply a format that promotes the collaborative spirit of participatory research and citizen science, and showcase what is being done in these domains by engaging attendees to become more than audience members to the conference. Inspired by the 'un-conference' approach that mobilises participants to be actively engaged in shaping the programme and content of an event together with the organisers, the conference sought to bring together all targeted types of stakeholders to 'Connect. Collaborate. Create.' pathways to shape the future of participatory research and citizen science.

The inspiration for this approach was drawn from the THATCamp (The Humanities and Technology Camp) model, which aims to encourage collaboration and concrete work with informal, on-the-spot planning, without lengthy proposals and a singular voice. Similar to the practices of participatory research and citizen science, this approach aims to open up the conversation for attendees to voice their needs and share their best practices.

The conference was set up from the beginning to stimulate an exchange of ideas and facilitate meaningful conversations that bridge communities; to activate participatory research and citizen science, particularly in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) and including funding challenges and opportunities; and exploring how we might enable, implement and assess these fields of research and innovation.

To guide participants around the topics of interest to be featured in the conference programme, the organising team elaborated three main themes in the form of questions we sought to address:

2.1.1 How do we support – “enable” – citizen science?

2.1.1.1 *PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH, CITIZEN SCIENCE AND OPEN SCIENCE NETWORKS AND INFRASTRUCTURES*

- ▶ What is the role of shared open science and responsible research and innovation principles and technologies? How can open and ethical approaches to service development and interoperability support citizen science at the national and European levels?
- ▶ What are the challenges and (potential) solutions to enabling collaborative research with and for society, both at the network and infrastructure level?
- ▶ How can connections and synergies among services and infrastructures be strengthened for the benefit of citizen science and participatory research practices?
- ▶ How do research funding schemes need to be transformed to enable participatory research? How do the processes within funding agencies need to be transformed to allow for participation in their activities (such as strategy development, call definition, and proposal evaluation)?

2.1.1.2 *SUPPORT SERVICES FOR PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH AND CITIZEN SCIENCE*

- ▶ What are the concrete experiences of science shops, libraries, learning centres, citizen science platforms, funding agencies, the European university alliances and other support services in facilitating citizen science and participatory research?
- ▶ How do they support the catalysation of research demands from civil society?
- ▶ How do they enable research beyond academia, give visibility to projects and practices, support matchmaking, networking and community building, and facilitate interprofessional “translations”, especially for the benefit of those that do not do research on a regular basis?
- ▶ How can they nurture new articulations between the local, national and international dimensions, and facilitate scale jump, e.g. by supporting language changes and digital access?

2.1.2 How do we do – “implement” – citizen science and participatory research, including ethical participation in the activities of research funders?

2.1.2.1 *METHODOLOGIES FOR DOING AND TEACHING CITIZEN SCIENCE AND ETHICAL PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES TO RESEARCH, INCLUDING IN FUNDING AGENCIES*

- ▶ How do we do participatory research on the ground, especially within the social sciences and the humanities while taking into account ethical considerations?

- ▶ What methodologies work within and beyond disciplines? How are we pushing public humanities, participatory action research, cultural participatory research, digital participatory research, and other approaches to meet old and new challenges?
- ▶ How do we do/facilitate/support ethical participation in the activities of funding organisations?
- ▶ What are the strengths of formats like citizen science academies, mutual learning exercises and diverse capacity building initiatives to facilitate and raise the profile of citizen science and participatory research, including those fostering participatory approaches to funding?

2.1.2.2 DATA WORKFLOWS AND COMMUNICATION FORMATS

- ▶ How can the (meta-) data produced in citizen science activities enter and be made available via digital open science spaces? How can it be made accessible as an evidence-base to inform policy decisions?
- ▶ How can it be aligned with existing standards and processes, and how might these standards and processes need to change to accommodate citizen generated data?
- ▶ What are the commonalities and differences between the challenges encountered by ethics and research assessment committees, research infrastructures, and citizen science service and platforms, and how might their roles change to address these?
- ▶ What visions exist for fitting innovative scholarly communication formats to citizen science and participatory research, especially those taking into account the non-digital dimensions of many citizen science activities in SSH?

2.1.2.3 DRIVERS AND BARRIERS FOR IMPLEMENTING, SUPPORTING, AND FUNDING CITIZEN SCIENCE, AS WELL AS PARTICIPATION IN THE PROCESSES OF THE FUNDING AGENCIES

- ▶ What ethical and institutional challenges, but also opportunities, arise when implementing participatory research and participation in the activities of funders?
- ▶ What commonalities and differences emerge from different framework conditions, goals, employed methodologies, and collaboration with different stakeholder groups?
- ▶ How can participation in research and research funding be made attractive?
- ▶ How can we involve new and underserved communities and empower them to make decisions even in situations with little leeway to do so? How can we do so in typically underserved fields like the social sciences and humanities?
- ▶ How do we rethink the roles of ethics and research assessment committees and research infrastructures, and how might they address the changing requirements brought about by participatory approaches to research and research funding?

2.1.3 How do we assess and evaluate participatory processes?

2.1.3.1 ASSESSING AND EVALUATING PARTICIPATORY PROCESSES?

- ▶ What do we want to achieve through participatory research (funding), what can be achieved, and what are the limits of such processes?
- ▶ How do we measure our impacts, generate new impact metrics, and ascertain the quality and integrity of our participatory processes and their results? What might new evaluation paradigms look like that encourage initiatives to (re-)connect research and society while safeguarding the quality of these collaborations?
- ▶ Taking into account structural conditions, concrete processes and their outcomes, what role do specific funding tools such as cascade funding, prizes and crowdfunding play, and how can new funding schemes support the specificities of participatory research activities at different scales?
- ▶ What practical and ethical frameworks and guidelines do different stakeholders need to assess participatory processes? What role might self-assessment tools and independent lookout systems – such as the French “tiers-veilleurs” (third party watch dogs) – play?

Having these themes in mind, participants were invited to offer ideas and share how they would like to contribute to conversations on one or more of these topics. After we received an extensive number of valuable suggestions, these were combined to form a lively collaborative conference programme stretched over three days. The next sections delve into detail the process and the outcomes of this collaborative work.

3 Target audiences

Based on the task description, an initial concept note about the conference drafted by ZSI in cooperation with RCN developed a list of stakeholder groups to be included in the final conference. COESO similarly mapped out its conference target audience. Thus, one of the initial steps into the partnership was putting these two lists together and identifying overlaps. Since there was a considerable overlap between the respective target communities, this strengthened our conviction that a collaboration on the conference would be beneficial for both sides. For PRO-Ethics, this meant an extension of the initial stakeholder list, and thus an enrichment from the opportunity to disseminate the project results to additional related stakeholder communities such as citizen science practitioners. The final list of stakeholders, which the conference targeted and mentioned in all communication efforts, includes:

1. Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)
2. Citizen Science practitioners and supporters, including:
 - a. (SSH) Academic and professional researchers
 - b. Civil society professionals and organisations (e.g. journalists, artists, social services practitioners, NGOs dedicated to societal issues, social enterprises)
 - c. Engaged community members, citizen scientists and scholars
 - d. Open research infrastructure representatives
 - e. Librarians
 - f. Country-based and European citizen science platform and network coordinators
 - g. Science shop coordinators and staff members
3. Policymakers
4. Research managers
5. Research ethics committee members
6. Research integrity body members
7. Researchers from academia and the private sector

In total, a highly mixed audience of 218 people registered to the conference, with approximately 170 managing to attend on site.

4 Collaboration with the COESO project

As already mentioned, the 'Connect. Collaborate. Create. Conference' was organised in the form of a partnership between the PRO-Ethics and COESO projects. On the PRO-Ethics side, the aim of attaching the final conference to a bigger community event had been standing for a while after a suggestion during a meeting with EC representatives.

The initial suggestion was to attach the final conference to the NEC Forum that was planned to take place around October-November in Spain, as the country holding the presidency of the European Council. However, this collaboration proved difficult, in part because the Spanish planning team of the NEC Forum experienced considerable uncertainties regarding all aspects of planning, which in turn led to downstream effects for PRO-Ethics such as long response times and delays in decision-making. In the end, and in agreement with the EC policy officer, the teams at ZSI and RCN started to seek out other opportunities for meaningful partnership that would result in a mutual beneficial event.

While project representatives of PRO-Ethics and COESO knew each other from various networking events – including the regular exchange meetings organised by the Horizon-funded EU-Citizen.Science and ECS projects – the cooperation between the projects presented itself as an opportunity during a Horizon Results Booster (HRB) intervention. There, both project coordinators realised the overlapping timelines for the final project conferences, equally set for October 2023. After being approached by PRO-Ethics, the COESO team expressed its enthusiasm in building a partnership and so in late May, the conference organisation team came together for the first time in a virtual meeting to check for overlaps in the target audiences, aims and objectives, format, available budgets, etc. The result of these initial talks consisted in the creation of a bigger conference organisers team, including the coordinating organisations, task leads, and involved partners from both projects. While the concept development and most important decisions were made between all team members, for other concrete tasks, the work was divided among different people, e.g. communications, logistics and administration, community engagement, etc. To facilitate this cooperation, the team participated in biweekly conference calls and other ad-hoc calls, maintained regular e-mail exchanges, and used several collaborative tools.

One of these collaborative tools created from the beginning was a list of all the cost categories arising for the organisation and promotion of the conference. The organisers decided to divide costs broadly according to categories, instead of splitting all costs in half. In turn, PRO-Ethics covered e.g. merchandising and certain printing costs, media services, and translation, whereas COESO covered e.g. catering and note-takers. By a stroke of luck, the venue could be procured free of cost.

A list of all organising committee members divided among different tasks can be found here: <https://ccc.sciencesconf.org/resource/page/id/2>

5 Planning, communication and network engagement

Following the creation of the organising committee, division of tasks, and a decision of the main vision of the conference, the communication activities started through the creation of mutual communication channels and the launch of the call for participants and proposals. This included creation of a project website, participant registration forms, and a Miro-Board used to collect and visualise proposals for workshops and presentations from participants.

In terms of data handling, the bulk of the data was hosted in a COESO-administered Google Cloud, with access given only to the involved team members from either project. The two project teams refrained from sharing contacts acquired in the course of each action, but rather invited their respective stakeholder communities individually, to ensure a responsible handling of contact data and honouring the terms of both GDPR and the projects' data management plans. No sensitive data was shared between the projects.

5.1 Conference website

A first general information on the conference, its concept and the call for proposals was shared individually on both project websites, each following the style of their project identity. This allowed the teams to start sending out information and inviting participants while a common space for promoting and communicating on the conference was created. For these purposes, sciencesCONF was chosen as a platform service since it is both free of charge and allows for long-term conference documentation, as the web presence can continue even after a project ends. The conference website is accessible at: <https://ccc.sciencesconf.org/>

The structure of the conference website grew with time as the organisation of the conference progressed. In the beginning, it described the entire concept by mentioning the target audience, the opportunity to participate as a presenter, and gave insights on several topics and issues on which participants were invited to make submissions. It also presented the organising committee, practical information on travel logistics such as accommodation, moving around in Paris, etc. As the programme developed, the conference website was continuously updated including information on the speakers, types of sessions, titles, etc.

After the end of the conference, all main communication materials used to report on the conference (photos, videos, blogposts etc.) were integrated into this online space to tell the whole story of the event.

5.2 Call for proposals

As already mentioned in the previous sections, the conference concept was developed via a participatory approach in which the participants shape the programme by suggesting contributions around the topics defined by the organisers. After submitting their ideas in the course of the registration process, submissions were first filtered by the organisers, to check if the proposed idea fits to one of the conference themes. Then, participants were invited to collaborate on a Miro-Board. Miro is an collaborative online whiteboard which was used as a tool to visualise ideas, discover common interests and thematic overlaps, and allowed them to develop cooperations according to thematic proximity and overlapping interests. In other words, the promotion of collaborative approaches took place already at the planning stage of the conference. In addition to that, a YouTube video was created to describe the

whole collaborative aspects and further instruct participants on how to use Miro: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GHOHT-C3vGQ>

In total, 51 submissions involving around 130 people made it onto the Miro-Board, excluding poster sessions and curated panel discussions. These entailed different formats ranging from presentations to exhibitions and to workshops with different kinds of interactive methodologies. Following the THATCamps approach, while giving all participants a chance to make a contribution despite the limited amount of time, submissions were then clustered by the organising team – following expressed interests and thematic overlaps – into 27 thematically diverse sessions, forming workshops with multiple contributors. In other words, these workshops carried out in several parallel sessions brought together practitioners from all over the EU and other countries, to discuss different aspects of a certain topic. This provided a chance to initiate a collaboration and learn from others' perspectives already at the planning stage. Contrary to some initial concerns that merging proposals could be challenging, the results were very satisfactory, with most of the participants being happy with the suggested collaborators. In Annex 1, an overview of the programme and all the parallel sessions with names of contributors is provided.

5.3 Promotion and network engagement

To promote the conference and reach out to all stakeholder communities, the communications team, as part of the bigger organisation committee, laid out a detailed plan with timelines, channels and tools to be used for effective communication. This included social media communication (via Twitter and LinkedIn), project websites and a mutual conference website, newsletters, and direct e-mails to all stakeholders involved in each of the projects throughout their runtimes.

The first stage of the promotion included distributing a 'Save the Date' message via all channels in late June 2023. This included information on the overall objective of the conference, dates, and location, as well as a list of all the target audiences we wanted to invite.

For the next two weeks following the launch of the 'Save the Date' information, the team worked on further defining the goals and themes of the conference, creating the registration form, and more tailored communication materials. In mid-July, we were finally able to launch the Call for Participants and Submissions including the Google Forms for registration, conference website for information and Miro-Board for submissions. The initial registration deadline for submitting proposals was set for early September, with the registration deadline (without collaborating in the conference programme) was set for the end of September, in the knowledge that it might needed to be prolonged. In the end, the registration deadline was extended until the fourth of October, only two weeks before the conference was set.

While the registration was open, several graphical elements were created to engage various communities through social media, including posts on speakers, plenary sessions, titles of workshops, countdown to the conference, and so on. In addition to social media communication, direct contact to stakeholder communities was a very effective tool for reaching out to desired contributors. The communications team designed dedicated invitations in several languages, which were distributed to all partners of both projects to share among their respective networks. Partners own communication channels such as websites, blogs, newsletters, and social media were also used to promote the conference.

The community engagement on the side of PRO-Ethics was led by ZSI, RCN and Nesta. This included direct emails by each of the team members to their contacts as well as mass-emails to stakeholders previously involved in the project activities who had expressed an interest in receiving further information from the project. Of particular importance for the purposes of our project, and to reach out to our main target audiences, were the TAFTIE and Science Europe networks, both of which shared the invitation among their member organisations.

In total, the conference reached 218 registrations by early October, when the registration was finally closed. With that, the initially planned number of participants of both projects could be achieved. As expected, some of the registered people could not attend due to unforeseeable reasons – with the conference taking place in person during Covid-season and with official travel advisory offered by some states against travelling to Paris – leading to a total of around 170 people attending over the course of three days.

6 Conference programme

As already envisaged at the project proposal stages of both projects, the final conference aimed to be an interactive event consisting of different types of sessions to inspire and promote collaboration in the field of participatory research and citizen science. Thus, the organisers aimed to provide a broad spectrum of opportunities to learn from and be involved in the conference.

After an organisational welcome, project coordinators Stefanie Schuerz (PRO-Ethics) and Alessia Smaniotto (COESO) opened the conference by giving a detailed overview of the work done and the key results achieved in their respective projects. This part of the conference was streamed on YouTube and continues to be available on the [Operas YouTube channel](#). Following this comprehensive introduction, conference participants were invited to 'Connect. Collaborate. Create.' together in a variety of formats, including:

- ▶ 3 keynote speeches
- ▶ 2 plenary sessions on topics highly relevant to both projects,
- ▶ 27 parallel sessions allowing for all contributors to be actively involved in running workshops and exhibitions, and
- ▶ a poster session showcasing 16 posters.

As one of the main foci of the conference relied in the promotion of collaboration in this field, the organisers decided to further include speed-dating and matchmaking sessions on each of the three days, as well as additional activities such as a library tour and an art performance. A social program at the end of the first and second days could also add to the many opportunities for coming together in an informal setting and discussing potential future collaborations.

As already mentioned, the conference program had a fluid character, being shaped by the organisers of all the parallel sessions, and the final result seemed a highly satisfactory experience, as stated by most participants, covering many important dimensions of ethical participatory engagement in research and innovation. Annex 1 shows in detail the various sessions implemented throughout the three conference days, while Annex 2 shows a visual representation of the program as provided to the participants during the conference.

7 Reporting and dissemination

The communication plan of the conference covered communication tools, materials, and mechanisms to raise awareness on the conference before, during and after its completion. Social media communication was an ongoing communication means during all three days for instantly sharing information on each of the sessions.

A tailored social media communication plan during the conference helped in reporting on each of the sessions on both the PRO-Ethics and COESO accounts on Twitter. At least one post was published on each of the sessions, however multiple posts were shared by the team and the participants. To channel all the social media posts from participants, we created the [#Collaborate4Research](#) hashtag and integrated it in the communication materials provided to the participants upon registration. Many of the conference participants were also very active in sharing content, using the conference hashtag and tagging both projects' accounts during all three days. Twitter was chosen as the main communication channel, as this was the channel both projects worked to establish a presence on throughout their projects' runtimes. In addition, the PRO-Ethics LinkedIn channel was continuously updated with contents from the consortium and posts from conference participants.

Another means of communication during the conference was a livestream set up to broadcast the conference opening, the three keynote speeches, the two plenary sessions, as well as a policy roundtable organised as a parallel session. Furthermore, a production firm was engaged to photographically document the conference and take video-recordings throughout the various sessions. In addition to the visual documentation, a note-taker was assigned to each of the sessions to record the main arguments and findings and allow the organisers to produce a proceedings document. Finally, participants had the opportunity to send the organising team a blog post summarising their experiences with the conference, as another means of documentation and dissemination. In the below sections, each of these is described briefly.

7.1 Livestream

Livestreaming during the conference was an instrument for reaching out to stakeholders not able to attend it and as a reporting tool. Due to logistical reasons, the organising team decided to livestream only the plenary sessions (including opening speeches, keynote speeches and plenary panels) and the policy roundtable set in the main theatre, since covering all sessions exceeded our capacities. For streaming, we used the Operas Research Infrastructure (part of the COESO project) YouTube channel, which was already actively operational. In total, 8 videos of the above-mentioned sessions were produced and are now available under the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLNSNT11cPt5YbgQ6Vdke2dsJKuSVACFpE>

7.2 Photos and video

As mentioned previously, photography and videography services were commissioned by PRO-Ethics to capture conference highlights and experience, and allow us to tell the story after its completion. The service was provided with the kind partnership of Ereb Media, which provided a photographer to cover all sessions and videographer to cover only the plenary sessions and a selection of the parallel sessions.

A selection of the main highlighting photos was included in the conference website: <https://ccc.sciencesconf.org/resource/gallery/id/16>

The aim of capturing video footage was to create a final conference video that shares some highlights from the conference. This video also created by Ereb Media and is available on the same YouTube channel as the livestreamed sessions. It can be accessed via the following link while also being embedded in the conference website and the PRO-Ethics website:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6rHLTVYFp9s&list=PLNSNT11cPt5YbgQ6Vdke2dsUKuSVACFpE&index=9>

7.3 Proceedings

After collecting all the notes provided by the note-takers assigned to each of the sessions – and with kind support from both panel collaborators and colleagues from the COESO and PRO-Ethics projects – the organising team started drafting conference proceedings, which will be available in Zenodo in early January 2024. Starting with an introduction and summary of the main findings of the conference, the document further depicts the highlights and main arguments of each of the sessions, giving details on the involved collaborators and their affiliations. The proceedings are available under the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10372457>

7.4 Blogposts

The final instrument for reporting on the conference is a series of blogposts put together by participants. Under the name 'Voices of the CCC conference,' these short pieces written by conference participants themselves give some insights into their impressions, experiences, and learnings. The posts are available on the PRO-Ethics and COESO websites, while also being linked on the conference website. The following list provides an overview and links to each of the pieces:

- ▶ [Shaping participatory futures: what can funders do to facilitate meaningful participation in and with science & innovation? by Frederike Schmitz, Dec 14 2023](#)
- ▶ [The future is now: Citizen participation in R&I by Nyangala Zolho, Nov 27 2023](#)
- ▶ [Promoting citizen science and fostering ethical participatory approaches to research funding by Marina Angelaki, Nov 24 2023](#)
- ▶ [Reflections on the 'Connect. Collaborate. Create.' Conference from Science Europe by James Morris and Claire Salinas from Science Europe, Nov 24 2023](#)
- ▶ [Infrastructuring Participatory Research in the Social Sciences and Humanities: Bridge or Breach? – Katja Mayer Interview with Katja Mayer, Nov 22 2023](#)
- ▶ [Philosophizing Participatory Research- some questions raised at the COESO Conference 2023 by Lucia Ziglioli, Nov 20 2023](#)
- ▶ [Supporting Participatory Research in the SSH – a valuable piece of the puzzle by Nel Coleman, Nov 20 2023](#)
- ▶ [What makes a successful innovation? by Magdalena Wnuk, Nov 8 2023](#)

8 Outcomes

As we reflect on the 'Connect. Collaborate. Create.' Conference, it becomes evident that this event was not just another milestone in the journey of participatory research and citizen science. To put it in the words of a participant, it was an “inspiring”, “engaging” and “intense” experience that allowed for connections and the development of new projects in fields touched by ethical participatory research and citizen science.

The diverse range of stakeholders who participated, including researchers, research funding organisations, policymakers, industry representatives, civil society organisations, and citizens, played a crucial role in enriching the discussions and outcomes of the conference. Initially, the PRO-Ethics final conference was planned to have a minimum of 150 attendees. The approx. 170 participants present over the course of three days of the conference met and surpassed this number.

The conference's innovative format, inspired by the 'un-conference' approach, was a resounding success. Through its various sessions and discussions, the conference addressed critical issues at the heart of participatory research and citizen science. Topics ranging from ethical participatory approaches to research funding, to methodologies for implementing and assessing participatory processes were thoroughly explored. Meeting the main goals of our conference, these discussions provided ample opportunities to 'Connect. Collaborate. Create.', but also to learn and grow together.

The outcomes of the conference, as detailed in this report, are proof for its success. The feedback from participants collected live via the Mentimeter platform during the closing session, indicated a high level of engagement and satisfaction, suggesting that the conference not only met but exceeded expectations. A few screenshots from the Mentimeter below serve to give insight into the atmosphere of the conference, while a summary of experiences with quotes from the participants has been included in the conference video available on YouTube (see link in the previous chapter). After the event itself, the organisers created a survey for all participants, with detailed questions on their experiences with the event. As is usually the case with post-event surveys, the return-rate was rather low, with only 22 participants completing it in its entirety. Still, the feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with participants singling out via the open questions the many interesting conversations they could join – or had to miss, due to the nature of parallel sessions. Similarly, the networking and discussion opportunities within and beyond communities were brought up repeatedly by participants. Various responses received via the survey state, e.g.:

“All the people I met at the conference were absolutely amazing. I am so glad I came!”, “it was a particularly diverse attendance in terms of organisation, which was very beneficial!”, “conversations with people working at Research Councils, Funding Bodies, and in research support roles at Universities was particularly interesting and insightful”, “It was a pity to select only one workshop because they were overlapped...I would attend all of them!!!”, “the only flaw in the balance was the age-old problem of too many sessions to choose from, and therefore the sense that much was missed - but solving that would have required more days of conference, which is unrealistic”

The dissemination of the conference's content through various channels, including live streaming, photos, videos, and blog posts, ensured that its impact extended well beyond the physical confines of the event. In conclusion, the 'Connect. Collaborate. Create.' Conference has not only contributed significantly to the discourse on ethical participatory research and citizen science, but has also charted a path forward for future endeavours in these fields.

8.1 Mentimeter feedback excerpts

New great networks onTrust	Meeting interesting people that we could work with	Participation is everywhere 🌍
Inspiration for new projects and curiosity about fields I don't know much more.	I met wonderful people in the ECSA association and found out about VERA	Train more in futures literacy and continue doing more futures literacy labs in the future
Super interesting and innovative use cases, pilots etc.	Complicity	
Participation is everywhere! Let's take care of it together!	Science with society, for society. We need to impact	New amazing people to develop new projects with.
Involving kids in research	We are the best community of practice ;)	Cool Community
Diversifying participatory research support	Understand positionality properly in order to build trust	Interdisciplinarity! Connections with other research domains.
VERA Platform!	It's time to create the right boxes and break down the ones that hurt	Connections with lots of practitioners!
More european cooperation	Don't be afraid of people :)	#TrustInScience rules
I had a project idea for including citizens in my research; And also new ideas for including in my daily work (collectively!)	Making sure to continue with this experience	New approaches how to use and present the Plastic Pirates data and links to policy.

8.2 Survey feedback excerpt

9) What was your most memorable experience or moment from the conference?

Annex 1: Conference programme

Keynote speeches

By invitation from the organisation team, three keynotes were provided during the first and second days of the conference:

Katja Mayer, University of Vienna, Centre for Social Innovation (ZSI)

Thursday, October 19th, 17:45-18:15

"Infrastructuring Participatory Research in the Social Sciences and Humanities: Bridge or Breach"

Katja Mayer is an Elise Richter Fellow at the University of Vienna's Department of Science and Technology Studies, where she explores the interface of science, technology, and society. She places particular emphasis on the politics of open science and data infrastructures. Trained as a sociologist, her current research focuses on the power of social scientific methods in the era of big data and machine learning. As an open science advocate, she actively advises on research and innovation policy. With prior experience in the IT industry, as a visiting fellow at Carnegie Mellon University, a research advisor to the President of the European Research Council, and a postdoc at TU Munich's Chair of Computational Social Sciences and Big Data, she is well-versed in both the practical and theoretical aspects of her field. Furthermore, she is a senior scientist at the Center for Social Innovation (ZSI) in Vienna and a member of the Uni Vienna research platform Governance of Digital Practices

Morgan Meyer, Mines Paris Tech

Friday, October 20th, 09:15-09:45

"Making Space for Citizen Science"

Morgan Meyer is a research director at the French CNRS and works at the Centre for the Sociology of Innovation at Mines Paris (PSL). His research focuses on the production of knowledge and technology outside or at the boundaries of established scientific institutions, with a concentration on three main topics:

- ▶ participation and co-production of knowledge, touching upon areas such as natural history, do-it-yourself biology, open-source agriculture, and low-tech innovations
- ▶ new configurations and communities in biology, including synthetic biology and gene editing
- ▶ intermediation, translation, and representation of knowledge

Morgan earned his PhD in Sociology from the University of Sheffield and served as a lecturer at Agro ParisTech. He has also been a visiting professor at the University of Vienna's Department of Science and Technology Studies and a visiting researcher at the University of Edinburgh's Genomics Forum.

Marzia Mazzonetto, Stickydot

Friday, October 20th, 17:15-17:45

"Expecting the unexpected: challenges in multi-stakeholder engagement"

Marzia Mazzonetto is the CEO of Stickydot srl, a Brussels-based SME specializing in multi-stakeholder engagement for research and innovation. Her dedication lies in ensuring comprehensive representation, making sure every voice is heard during the co-creation of research and innovation strategies. These strategies aim to address pressing societal challenges of our era.

Marzia coordinates the H2020 EU-funded project, MOSAIC (Mission-Oriented SwafS to Advance Innovation through Co-creation). This project implements multi-stakeholder co-creation processes, pinpointing solutions for cities participating in the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission.

Furthermore, she co-led the development of the EU-Citizen.Science platform for the European Citizen Science Association. Marzia also served on the Forum for Research and Innovation, providing insights on the responsible governance of research and innovation for the Lombardy regional government. Additionally, she contributed as an expert to the Mutual Learning Exercise on the Citizen Science initiative led by the European Commission.

Plenary sessions

In addition to the keynote speeches, the programme included two plenary panels, reflecting two highlighted topics of the conference: 1) supporting citizen science in the social sciences and humanities and 2) participatory approaches to funding. The below paragraphs describe the titles of the sessions as well as participants and their affiliations.

Thursday 11:00-12:15, Centre des Colloques Auditorium 250

'What does it take to make citizen science grow? Models and experiences in support of participatory practices.'

- ▶ **Moderated by Alessia Smaniotto**, EHESS, COESO Coordinator
- ▶ **Annelies Duerinckx**, Scivil
- ▶ **Martine Legris**, Université de Lille
- ▶ **Nel Coleman**, University of Edinburgh Library
- ▶ **Muki Haklay**, ECSA, Université Paris Cité/ Learning Planet Institute, ECS - European Citizen Science project/EU-Citizen.Science

Friday 9:40-10:40, MSH Auditorium 300

'When funding agencies do stakeholder participation: Aspirations and ethical implications'

- ▶ **Moderated by Margaret Gold**, Leiden University
- ▶ **Juliana Chaves Chaparro**, UNESCO
- ▶ **Robert Gianni**, Maastricht University
- ▶ **Anne-Floor Scholvinck**, Rathenau Institut

- ▶ **James Morris**, Science Europe

Parallel sessions

The parallel sessions consisted of 27 workshops running throughout the three conference days, designed by the participants with the guidance and leadership of the organisation committee. Below we provide an overview of all these sessions.

Session 1.1: Thursday, Oct. 19th, 14:30 - 16:00

Participatory practices and local engagement: the role of community-based organisations

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Muki Haklay**, Université Paris Cité/ Learning Planet Institute
- ▶ **Alexandra Albert**, Nesta, Centre for Collective Intelligence Design
- ▶ **Sara Dewachter**, University of Antwerp
- ▶ **Kelly Achenbach**, Max Weber Stiftung

Stakeholder participation in R&I and citizen science: opportunities and responsibilities from a policy perspective

Stakeholder participation in research and innovation cannot be successful without support from policy. This policy roundtable opens the conversations on the opportunities brought forth by supporting participation in R&I, while also highlighting the responsibilities policymakers have to enable a more open, democratic scientific system.

Panelists:

- ▶ **Marina Angelaki**, University of Peloponnese (MODERATOR)
- ▶ **Ana Persic**, UNESCO Open Science Team
- ▶ **Moritz Müller**, Bürger schaffen Wissen
- ▶ **René von Schomberg**, Aachen University of Technology
- ▶ **Krista Varantola**, ALLEA, Finnish Academy of Science and Letters

Participatory evaluation and self-assessment applied to citizen science

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Dominique Boullier**, Sciences Po, COESO project
- ▶ **Jessica Pidoux**, Sciences Po, PersonalData.IO, COESO project
- ▶ **Barbara Kieslinger**, ZSI - Centre for Social Innovation
- ▶ **Florence Belaen**, Université Lumière Lyon 2

From experimental support services for participatory research to institutional citizen science hubs

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Nel Coleman**, University of Edinburgh Library
- ▶ **Morgane Montagnat**, Université Lumière Lyon 2 Science Shop
- ▶ **Aelita Skarzauskiene**, Vilnius Gediminas Technical University

Supporting participatory research practices in the SSH with VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation)

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Tiziana Lombardo**, Net 7
- ▶ **Luca De Santis**, Net7
- ▶ **Marlen Töpfer**, Max Weber Stiftung

Participatory research storytelling and transmedia journeys

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **William Costello**, Freelance UX designer
- ▶ **Camilo Leon Quijano**, CNRS/Université Aix-Marseille
- ▶ **Frédéric Vidal**, Universidade Autónoma de Lisboa

Session 2.1: Friday, Oct. 20th, 11:30 - 13:00

Co-created solutions for citizen science platforms

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Tiziana Lombardo**, Net7
- ▶ **Lucrina Stefanescu**, Babes-Bolyai University Cluj-Napoca
- ▶ **Jorge Barba**, Ibercivis
- ▶ **Sy Holsinger**, OPERAS
- ▶ **Liubov Tupikana**, Learning Planet Institute, Nokia Bell Labs

Data justice and ethics with participatory research communities

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Gefion Thuermer**, King's College London
- ▶ **Simon Hoyte**, University College London
- ▶ **Shubhangi Kumari**, Urban Institute

Participatory citizen science futures

Session Collaborators:

- ▶ **Alexandra Albert**, Nesta, IMPETUS project

Mainstreaming and strengthening citizen science: how do we develop policy engagement strategies across Europe?

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Marius Oesterheld**, Museum für Naturkunde Berlin

Learning participatory research: creating common spaces for training and mutual learning

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Martine Legris**, Université de Lille/CERAPS, Science Shop Lille
- ▶ **Alexandra Villarroel-Parada**, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Réseau Particip-Arc
- ▶ **Stephanie Bost**, Trait d'union, Boutique des Sciences MSH SUD
- ▶ **Sebastian Harnacker**, TU Wien Bibliothek/Vienna Library
- ▶ **Cléa Montanari**, Université Paris Cité/ Learning Planet Institute
- ▶ **Muki Haklay**, Université Paris Cité/ Learning Planet Institute
- ▶ **Alessia Smaniotto**, EHESS, COESO project

Putting the PRO-Ethics framework and guidelines into practice

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Stefanie Schuerz**, ZSI - Centre for Social Innovation
- ▶ **Constanze Fetting**, ZSI - Centre for Social Innovation
- ▶ **Alex Glennie**, Innovation Growth Lab/Nesta
- ▶ **Nyangala Zolho**, Innovation Growth Lab/Nesta
- ▶ **Lisa Häberlein**, EUREC Office

Session 2.2: Friday, Oct. 20th, 14:15 - 15:45

Transcriptions participatives: plateformes, publics, méthodes

This session was held in French.

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Alyx Taounza-Jeminet**, Humathèque Condorcet
- ▶ **Jean-Pierre Girard**, Maison de l'Orient et de la Méditerranée/Archéorient
- ▶ **Eva Perez**, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle/RECOLNAT

Participatory inquiries: what research does to journalism, and vice versa

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Mathilde Dorcadie**, Cafébabel, Equal Times, Freelance journalist
- ▶ **Lorenzo Bagnoli**, IRPI - Investigative Reporting Project Italy
- ▶ **Fabrice Rizzoli**, Crim'HALT
- ▶ **Michele Riccardi**, Crime&Tech, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore/Transcrime

Digital humanities, citizen science and the arts: synergies towards innovative formats

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Magdalene Wnuk**, IBL PAN, OPERAS-PL
- ▶ **Clarisse Bardiot**, Université Rennes 2
- ▶ **Chiara Girlando**, EHESS

Shaping participatory futures: what can funders do to facilitate meaningful participation in and with science & innovation?

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Floriant Covelli**, Institut français du Monde associatif
- ▶ **Anne-Floor Scholvinck**, Rathenau Instituut
- ▶ **Frederike Schmitz**, NWO (Dutch Research Council)
- ▶ **Anila Nauni**, Research Council Norway
- ▶ **Thomas Evenson**, Research Council Norway
- ▶ **Nyangala Zolho**, Innovation Growth Lab/Nesta
- ▶ **Alex Glennie**, Innovation Growth Lab/Nesta
- ▶ **Esther Baar**, Rathenau Instituut

Frontiers of action research with underrepresented communities

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Patricia Martinez Galisteo**, Fisabio Foundation
- ▶ **Reidun Norvoll**, Oslo Metropolitan University (OsloMet)
- ▶ **Benoit Eyraud**, Université Lumière Lyon 2
- ▶ **Bartolomeo Conti**, EHESS/CEMS

Virtues and limits of current impact assessment methods: a new approach towards measuring change

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Stefanie Schuerz**, ZSI - Centre for Social Innovation
- ▶ **Maria-Ascension Bajares**, CDTI
- ▶ **Simon Apartis**, CNRS/Centre Internet et société
- ▶ **Antonella Passani**, T6 Ecosystems
- ▶ **Barbara Kieslinger**, ZSI - Centre for Social Innovation

Session 3.1: Saturday, Oct 21st, 9:10-10:40

Responsive ethics and participation - current and future challenges

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Bernard Reber**, SciencesPo/CEVIPOF
- ▶ **Charlotte Bruns**, Rotterdam Erasmus School of History, Culture and Communication

- ▶ **Simone Driessen**, Rotterdam Erasmus School of History, Culture and Communication
- ▶ **Reda Cimperman**, Research Council of Lithuania
- ▶ **Julija Baniukevič**, Research Council of Lithuania

Working with vulnerable groups in innovation policy processes and citizen science formats

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Adele De Stefani**, Association ISRAA
- ▶ **Isabella Riccò**, Rovira i Virgili University
- ▶ **Sebastian Harnacker**, TU Wien Bibliothek/Vienna Library
- ▶ **Steph Grohmann**, LBG OIS Center
- ▶ **Julian Stubbe**, VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH
- ▶ **Markus Gerold**, VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH
- ▶ **Bettina Schmietow**, VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH

How to involve children in shaping our world

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Lucia Ziglioli**, FilosoficamenteLab
- ▶ **Ángel Arenas**, Giant Interactive Maps
- ▶ **Frida Sanga**, Aqua Farms Organization
- ▶ **Isabelle Dufrene**, School teacher, member of the Direction du numérique pour l'éducation

River Health – Citizen Science to monitor environmental policies

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Simone Berk**, DLR-PT
- ▶ **Enock Kiminta** (*online contribution*), Kenya National Association of Water Resources Users Association (KeNAWRUA)

Créations collectives et inclusives dans des contextes locaux

This session was held in French.

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Vincent Puig**, IRI – *Sciences participatives et recherche contributive dans le champs de l'alimentation à Saint-Denis*
- ▶ **Yahya Al-Abdullah**, EHESS – *A memory for the Future*
- ▶ **Thomas Tari**, SciencesPo/médialab – *Le champ des possibles, une enquête collective à Sevran*
- ▶ **Robin de Mourat**, SciencesPo/médialab – *Le champ des possibles, une enquête collective à Sevran*
- ▶ **Clémence Seurat**, SciencesPo/médialab – *Le champ des possibles, une enquête collective à Sevran*

Session 3.2: Saturday, Oct 21st, 11:00-12:30

Dancing Philosophy / Dansophie: atelier de danse et de philosophie

This session was mainly in French, some English translation was provided.

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Stefania Ferrando**, Université Côte d'Azur
- ▶ **Cosetta Graffione**, Cadmium Compagnie

A town by the sea: gaming climate change

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Lucija Klaric**, Culture Hub Croatia
- ▶ **Marina Batinic**, Culture Hub Croatia

Establishing trust and applying tools for community engaged research, policy, and practice

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Elsa Falkenburger**, Urban Institute
- ▶ **Teresa Deubelli-Huang**, IIASA | International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis

When participatory approaches inspire new formats for communicating science

Session collaborators:

- ▶ **Ayda Cecilia Padilla López**, Universidad de Guadalajara
- ▶ **Mathilde Dorcadie**, Freelance Journalist, Equal Times
- ▶ **Francesca Festa**, Co-Founder of Ereb Media and Sphera Network
- ▶ **Alessia Smaniotto**, EHES, COESO and PLACES projects coordinator

Poster sessions

In addition to the previously mentioned sessions, a poster session with a dedicated timeslot gave the opportunity to present the posters submitted during the registrations process. In total, 16 posters were submitted. They were showcased in one of the conference locations, at the Humathèque, on the first and the second day of the conference. On the first day, dinner took place in the same room the posters were exhibited in, while on the second day, a dedicated poster session was held in the evening. The list below provides an overview of the title and presenters of all submitted posters.

- ▶ *Visual Narrative Days* presented by **Camilo Patiño García**, University of Guadalajara
- ▶ *Co-creation for regional energy transitions - Experiences from the RIPEET project*, presented by **Constanze Fetting**, Centre for Social Innovation
- ▶ *Exploring the power of participation for trust in science*, presented by **Teresa Deubelli-Hwang**, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis

-
- ▶ Supporting Citizen Science through Citizen Science Hub: lessons learned from TIME4CS project, presented by **Professor Dr. Egle Butkeviciene**, Kaunas University of Technology
 - ▶ Citizen social science as a tool for youth social inclusion: case of Lithuania, presented by **Professor Dr. Egle Butkeviciene**, Kaunas University of Technology
 - ▶ OPERAS Innovation Lab: Supporting Innovative Scholarly Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities, presented by **Maciej Maryl**, Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences
 - ▶ How does mass tourism change the Lisbon's António district? presented by **Frédéric Vidal**, Autonomous University of Lisbon
 - ▶ How do we think with our body? presented by **Stefania Ferrando**, Côte d'Azur University
 - ▶ How does the italian law on the social use of confiscated mafia assets enable citizen participation? presented by **Mathilde Dorcadie**, Cafebabel
 - ▶ Tools and databases to increase the impact of investigative journalism presented by **Lorenzo Bagnoli**, Irpi Media
 - ▶ Growing Migrant Knowledge: Contemporary and Historical Perspectives presented by **Daniel Burckhardt**, GHI Washington
 - ▶ Digital Mapping with Disabled Citizens presented by **Julia Bruegemann**, HS Gesundheit
 - ▶ Ageing in a Caring Community presented by **Isabella Riccò & Adele De Stefani**, Rovira i Virgili University, Istituto per Servizi di Ricovero e Assistenza agli Anziani
 - ▶ Mapping water quality from the river to the glass in Tanzania presented by **Sara Dewachter**, University of Antwerp, IOB
 - ▶ Playful futures. Raising awareness about climate change issues through gaming activities presented by **Matteo Uguzzoni**
 - ▶ Lunch Box Monitor: Insight into the nutritional quality of school lunch-boxes to assess food insecurity among primary school children in Belgium presented by **Prof. Dr. Dieneke van de Sompe**, Ghent University

Annex 2: Designed conference programme

2023
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

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Bridging communities to foster participatory research and citizen science

SCHEDULE

Thursday, October 19, 2023

08:00 - 09:00	Welcome Check-in	COLL Entrance lobby
09:00 - 09:45	Conference opening & institutional welcome Alessia Smaniotto , EHESS, COESO coordinator Hélène Le Roux , EHESS, Director of the Research development dept. French Ministry of Research, representative from Research and Society Unit (TBD) European Commission representative (TBC)	COLL 250
09:45 - 10:15	PRO-Ethics project objectives & results Stefanie Schuerz , ZSI, PRO-Ethics coordinator	COLL 250
10:15 - 10:45	COESO project objectives & results Alessia Smaniotto , EHESS, COESO coordinator	COLL 250
10:45-11:30	Coffee break	EHESS Mezzanine
11:30 - 12:45	Plenary Panel <i>What does it take to make citizen science grow?</i> <i>Models and experiences in support of participatory practices</i> Annelies Duerinckx , Scivil Martine Legris , University de Lille Niel Coleman , University of Edinburgh Library	COLL 250
12:45 - 14:30	Lunch	<i>Crous University Restaurant</i>

2023
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

Bridging communities
to foster participatory
research and citizen science

SCHEDULE

Thursday, October 19, 2023

- 14:30 - 16:00** **Parallel Sessions 1.1**

1.1A *Participatory practices and local engagement: the role of community based organisations*

1.1B *Panel discussion: Stakeholder participation in R&I and citizen science: opportunities and responsibilities from a policy perspective*

1.1C *Participatory Evaluation and self-assessment applied to citizen science*

1.1D *Citizen Science Hubs and desirable futures for participatory approaches*

- 16:00 - 16:30** **Coffee break** EHES Mezzanine

- 16:30 - 17:15** **Speed Searching** EHES Mezzanine

Like the matchmakers of the times, like modern matchmaking algorithms, we'll grow your network to build bridges between your interests or brainstorm new research projects. During this activity, you meet other people in the conference and chat for a short time with them as they try to decipher your participatory project by asking you the questions they want or that the moderator has put forward. The audience is invited to meet another participatory research enthusiast every 7-8 minutes. (This event was inspired by the European Researchers' Night.)

Photo exhibit EHES Lobby

Library tour HUM Lobby

- 17:15 - 17:45** "Be Seated" Performance COLL 250

- 17:45 - 18:15** **Keynote - Katja Mayer** COLL 250

Infrastructuring Participatory Research in the Social Sciences and Humanities: Bridge or Breach?

- 18:30 - 20:00** **Dinner** HUM Lobby

2023
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Connect laborate create

Bridging communities
to foster participatory
research and citizen science

SCHEDULE

Friday, October 20, 2023

08:30 - 09:00	Welcome Check-in	COLL Entrance lobby
09:00 - 09:45	Keynote - Morgan Meyer <i>Making Space for Citizen Science</i>	MSH Auditorium
09:45 - 11:00	Plenary Panel <i>When funding agencies do stakeholder participation: Aspirations and ethical implications</i> Moderated by Margaret Gold , Leiden University Juliana Chaves Chaparro , UNESCO Robert Gianni , Maastricht University Anne-Floor Scholvinck , Rathenau Institut James Morries , Science Europe	MSH Auditorium
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break	MSH Salle panoramique
11:30 - 13:00	Parallel Sessions 2.1 2.1G <i>Community-driven solutions for citizen science platforms and infrastructures</i> 2.1H <i>Handling citizen science data and ethics</i> 2.1I <i>Transcriptions participatives: methodes, outils, plateformes</i> 2.1J <i>Mainstreaming and strenghtening Citizen Science: how do we develop policy engagement strategies across Europe?</i> 2.1K <i>Learning participatory research: trainings and mutual learnings spaces</i> 2.1L <i>Putting the PRO-Ethics framework and guidelines into practice</i>	
13:00 - 14:15	Lunch	<i>Crous University Restaurant</i>

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research and citizen science

SCHEDULE

Friday, October 20, 2023

- 14:15 - 15:45** Parallel Sessions 2.2 (details on all sessions here)
- 2.2M** *Participatory Inquiries: What research does to journalism, and vice versa*
 - 2.2N** *Digital humanities, citizen science and the arts: synergies towards innovative formats*
 - 2.2O** *Potential and challenges of participatory approaches to research funding*
 - 2.2P** *Frontiers of action research with frontiers publics*
 - 2.2Q** *Virtues and limits of current impact assessment methods: A new approach towards measuring change*
- 15:45 - 16:15** **Coffee Break** **HUM** Lobby
- 16:15 - 17:00** Poster Session **HUM** Lobby
- 17:00-17:15** Walk and Talk: group walk to keynote session
- 17:15 - 17:45** Keynote- **Marzia Mazzonetto** **MSH** Auditorium
Expecting the unexpected: challenges in multi-stakeholder engagement
- 18:00 - 18:45** Speed Searching (networking opportunity) **MSH** Salle panoramique
Like the matchmakers of the times, like modern matchmaking algorithms, we'll grow your network to build bridges between your interests or brainstorm new research projects. During this activity, you meet other people in the conference and chat for a short time with them as they try to decipher your participatory project by asking you the questions they want or that the moderator has put forward. The audience is invited to meet another participatory research enthusiast every 7-8 minutes.
(This event was inspired by the European Researchers' Night)

2023
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Bridging communities
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research and citizen science

SCHEDULE

Friday, October 20, 2023

- 18:45** **Individual Networking/ Social Dinner** Various locations
- Looking for a social networking opportunity or an evening with other participatory research and citizen science enthusiasts? We've reserved tables for small groups of people at several restaurants in the famous Montmartre district. Would you like to join a group? Sign up at the registration desk. (Please note: this is a self-pay activity; the conference is not covering any costs.)*

Saturday, October 21, 2023

- 08:30 - 09:00** Welcome Check-in **MSH Hall**
- 09:00 - 10:30** Parallel Sessions 3.1
- 3.1R** *Responsive ethic and ethical dilemmas in participatory research*
 - 3.1S** *Citizen science with vulnerable participants*
 - 3.1T** *Child-focused participatory research*
 - 3.1U** *Citizen science for water health*
 - 3.1V** *Créations collectives et inclusives dans des contextes locaux*
- 10:30 - 11:00** **Coffee break** **MSH Salle panoramique**
- 11:00 - 12:30** Parallel Sessions 3.2
- 3.2W** *Dansophie: atelier de danse et philosophie*
 - 3.2X** *A town by the sea: gaming climate change*
 - 3.2Y** *Decision-making tools for community engagement and trust in science*
 - 3.2Z** *When participatory approaches inspire new formats for communicating science*
- 12:30 - 13:15** Closing Session **MSH Auditorium**
- 13:15 - 14:00** **Lunch bag & Goodbye** **MSH Auditorium**

Annex 3: Communication materials

2023
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

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Bridging communities
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research and citizen
science

**19 OCTOBER
TO
21 BER**

PARIS
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Campus
Condorcet

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coeso connecting research and society **proEthics**

Venue and logistic support
generously provided by **CAMPUS CONDORCET** **HUMATHÈQUE** **L'ÉCOLE DES SCIENCES SOCIALES**

COESO and PRO-Ethics have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements 101006325 and 872441

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Bridging communities
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research and citizen science

CONFERENCE MAP

Aubervilliers Campus Condorcet

2023

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

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Bridging communities to foster
participatory research
and citizen science

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PARIS
Aubervilliers
Campus Condorcet

coeso **proEthics**
connecting research and society